

SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

User Story

View the
presentation

Localizando herramientas/ Localizing tools

Trying out

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What

The SSH Open Marketplace provides a lot of information about Digital Humanities (DH) tools, but it may be hard to navigate for lay DH users, particularly for uninitiated colleagues and students, i.e. most of the Humanistic academy: descriptions are often minimal or cryptic, with very technical keywords and no information about the level of complexity, and, of course, almost always in English. Last but not least, redirecting users to a complex Github repo may overestimate their digital literacy. This is our proven experience with colleagues and even at a master's degree level. Users should be able to identify the most friendly tools and understand their functioning quickly and easily; and to do so, we need not only filters for categories, activities, or keywords, but also by levels of user-friendliness. To disseminate the use of the SSH Open Marketplace, we propose some tips and bottom-up strategies.

Who

We are three researchers from Complutense University of Madrid (Spain) working within the [LEETHI project](#) and coming from a master's degree in [Letras Digitales](#). Based on our experience, we are targeting Spanish-speaking students, scholars, and researchers in Social Sciences and Humanities who are not familiar with DH and need some guidance to find the resources that are already available.

How

Our project is planned on three stages and deliverables: (1) a user experience analysis to detect current limitations in the design of SSH Open Marketplace, (2) a prototype with icons for different levels of difficulty for a more complete and accessible SSH Open Marketplace, (3) a sample of clear descriptions in Spanish for less tech-savvy users.

When

We want to present to different audiences tools adapted to their skills. They could be included in our teaching and consulting programs: from high school and citizen science experiences, ranging from Ph.D. candidates to senior researchers not digitally skilled. We target specific audiences, but larger and reaching beyond the traditional boundaries of DH. Starting from the bottom, we are releasing several [introductory courses](#) on DH for senior citizens to make digital environments accessible for them. Likewise, we will disseminate our knowledge of the SSH Open Marketplace throughout the Spanish-speaking academic community, for example, leveraging networks such as [HDH](#) and targeting specific teams.

Try the SSH Open Marketplace

www.sshopencloud.eu

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